

Assessing walking ability in broilers on farm

ANIVET

Walking ability influences broiler welfare

Walking ability is a highly important animal-based indicator of welfare in broilers. Impaired walking ability can hinder birds' capability to access resources such as food and water, prevent them from performing motivated behaviours, are linked with increased morbidity and mortality rates and may be associated with pain (EFSA AHAW Panel et al., 2023).

Below, the protocols for gait scoring and the latency to lie test for assessing walking ability are described. Note that walking ability is dependent on age/body weight at the time of assessment, which should be taken into account if comparing across flocks.

Legal requirements

Council directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production:

“Chickens that are seriously injured or show evident signs of health disorder, such as those having **difficulties in walking**, severe ascites or severe malformations, and are likely to suffer, shall receive appropriate treatment or be culled immediately. [...]” (Annex I, Point 9)

Gait scoring

The Welfare Quality® Assessment Protocol for poultry includes a gait scoring method for broilers which is very similar to the original Bristol scale (Welfare Quality®, 2009). This method suggests using a catching pen in six random locations throughout the house to score a total of approximately 150 birds. Each bird should be

encouraged to walk out of the pen, one at a time. A flock average score is then calculated. Scoring is done according to the 6-point scale shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Gait scoring according to the Welfare Quality® assessment protocol (Welfare Quality®, 2009).

Score	Criteria
0	Normal, dexterous and agile
1	Slight abnormality, but difficult to define
2	Definite and identifiable abnormality
3	Obvious abnormality, affects ability to move
4	Severe abnormality, only takes a few steps
5	Incapable of walking

Fig. 1: Gait scoring performed with the use of a catching pen. Source: ANIVET

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Latency-to-lie test

The latency-to-lie test is a behavioural test for the assessment of leg health as a proxy of walking ability. This test consists of measuring the duration that birds can remain standing, with longer durations being associated with better walking ability (Wurtz & Riber, 2024). A flock average duration is calculated. The test can be conducted with or without a box.

With a box: Like for the gait scoring, a catching pen is used in six random locations throughout the house to score a total of approximately 100 birds. A bird is placed in standing position in a transparent box (no lid) with the bedding from the barn. A stopwatch is then started, and the latency until the bird sits down is recorded. The test bird is removed from the box after it sits down or after 300 s. Multiple birds may be scored simultaneously (in separate boxes) by the same observer.

Without a box: A sitting or lying bird is gently encouraged to stand up. A stopwatch is then started, and the latency until the bird sits down is recorded. The test is terminated if no attempt to sit is witnessed after 300 s. This is repeated in random locations throughout the house until approximately 100 birds are assessed.

Fig. 2: Latency-to-lie test using a box. The test has come to an end, as the broiler is sitting down. Source: ANIVET

Pros and cons of the described methods of assessing walking ability

Gait scoring remains the most widely used method due to its ease of being implemented on-farm. However, its subjectivity can make comparison between farms scored by different observers difficult. This has led to the development of the more objective latency-to-lie test that is highly linked with gait scores. The original protocol for the latency-to-lie test involved water in the boxes, but the method has now been validated with the use of a box containing bedding instead of water and without box. A summary of pros and cons of these methods is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Major positives and limitations of the methods of gait scoring and latency-to-lie for assessing walking ability. Validity, reliability, and feasibility estimates are also provided (low (+), moderate (++), high (+++)).

Method	Positives	Limitations	Validity	Reliability	Feasibility
Gait scoring	Low time requirement for the test itself, validated	Requires extensive training and catching pen, can have low reliability, can be difficult to perform reliably under high stocking density	+++	+ (+) ¹	+ (+) ¹
Latency-to-lie with box	Objective, validated, does not require training, easily implemented on farm, does not require forcing lame birds to walk	Requires catching pen and boxes	+++	+++	++
Latency-to-lie without box	Same as with a box. Time effective, no equipment is needed	Lower validity when performed without boxes versus with boxes	++	+++	+++

¹ Depending on the level of training and calibration – more training increases the reliability but decreases the feasibility.

References

- EFSA AHAW PANEL, et al. 2023. Welfare of broilers on farm. EFSA J, 21, e07788.
 WELFARE QUALITY® 2009. Welfare Quality assessment protocol for poultry. Welfare Quality Network.
 RIBER, A.B., RASMUSSEN, S., WURTZ, K.E. 2024. Latency-to-lie test without water is a valid objective method for on-farm assessment of walking ability of broilers. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14008430>

Co-funded by
the European Union

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

